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ON THE EFFICACY OF RIBLETS IN MITIGATING LOSSES DUE TO WAKE INDUCED TRANSITION OVER T106C BLADE

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ABSTRACT

A series of implicit large-eddy simulations (ILES) are performed on the T106C, an ultra-high-lift low-pressure turbine (UHLPT) cascade at $Re_C = 0.9 \times 10^5$ to investigate boundary-layer transition and loss mechanisms. Four configurations are considered: baseline (BL), baseline with wake passing (BLW), post-reattachment riblets (PoReRib), and peak-suction riblets (PeSuRib). In all cases except BL, upstream wakes were introduced to generate unsteady perturbations, to investigate their effects on the suction-side separation bubble, skin-friction behavior, and profile losses. The PoReRib and PeSuRib configurations further incorporate riblets on the suction side of the blade to study the combined effect of wakes and riblets on boundary layer transition and drag reduction. BLW offered the largest benefit with a reduction in total pressure loss of 14.1% compared to BL. Despite achieving lower skin-friction in the turbulent regime, ribbed blades are found to incur higher losses due to the early transition. Compared to the BLW, the PoReRib case increased losses by 10% whereas the PeSuRib case showed an overall increase of around 30%. Although time-averaged behavior depicts increased overall losses, the phase-averaged analysis reveals the benefit of riblets during certain phases associated with the bubble suppression by wakes.

NOMENCLATURE

UHLPT ultra-high-lift low-pressure turbine
FST free-stream turbulence
Re Reynolds number
 U_{bar} bar speed
 V_{2is} isentropic exit velocity
 C_{ax} axial chord
 C_p static pressure coefficient
 k turbulent Kinetic Energy
 s^+ riblet spacing in viscous units
 h^+ riblet height in viscous units
 ν dynamic viscosity
 u_τ friction velocity

1 Introduction

The low-pressure turbine (LPT) typically accounts for nearly 30% of an aircraft engine's weight. In modern high-bypass ratio engines, ultra-high-lift low-pressure turbine (UHLPT) blades with relatively increased blade loading and reduced blade count are often employed to achieve weight reduction and improve overall efficiency. In such designs, the suction surface is prone to boundary-layer separation, which increases profile losses and reduces the aerodynamic efficiency. Owing to the large aspect ratios of LPT blades, typically between 3

and 7 : 1, the profile loss is the dominant contributor to overall efficiency loss. In fact, separation over the suction surface of UHLPT blades can account for nearly 60% of the total loss [1,2].

The characteristics of the laminar separation bubble (LSB) are strongly dependent on operating conditions. Parameters such as the Reynolds number (Re) [3, 4], surface roughness [5–7], free-stream turbulence (FST), and upstream wake interactions [8–10] significantly affect bubble formation, transition, and reattachment. For LPT blades operating at low Re , external disturbances such as FST and wakes may reduce the bubble size to some extent, but cannot entirely eliminate the separation [11]. Himmel’s [12] experiments on the T106C cascade confirmed similar behavior for $Re < 100,000$, with persistent separation even under wake-dominated inflow conditions.

To attain further benefits apart from wake-induced transition, Montomoli et al. [13] investigated the combined effect of wakes and roughness. However, they noticed that roughness at low Re had minimal impact on the transition. Moreover, active and passive flow-control strategies have been investigated to reduce profile losses. Active techniques, such as slot blowing [14], vortex-generator jets [15, 16], and plasma-based flow control [17], have demonstrated effectiveness in suppressing LSB. However, Bons. et al [18] observed that these flow-control methods offer benefits at low FST; however, their performance diminishes under elevated levels of turbulence and strong unsteady wakes. Passive devices, including surface roughness elements and boundary-layer trip wires, can trigger earlier transition but might often incur additional local losses depending on the operating Re . Himmel [12] examined the use of depression-type riblets on the T106C blade and reported minimal influence on overall loss compared to elevated riblet geometries, particularly when applied in a spanwise manner, where boundary-layer losses are inherently higher [19].

More recently, Ananth et al. [20–22] investigated the suction surface boundary layer under various LPT blade loadings by subjecting a flat surface to a controlled streamwise varying pressure gradient imposed via contoured walls. Their work highlighted three key findings: (a) riblets embedded beneath the local surface can minimize losses more effectively than riblets protruding from the surface, (b) scalloped riblets outperform sawtooth riblets, reducing skin-friction drag by nearly 10%, and (c) scalloped riblets with $s^+ \approx 17$ and $h^+ \approx 22$ achieved a net skin-friction reduction of 7.3% and a 14.5% decrease in trailing-edge momentum thickness, respectively. The current study extends this strategy of employing the riblets on a turbine blade and verifies their performance on a T106C cascade. In addition, we evaluate the efficacy of riblets under the influence of upstream wakes.

2 METHODOLOGY

Scale-resolving simulations over a T106C cascade are carried out using COMPSQUARE, a high-order, structured

TABLE 1. Cascade Specifications for T106C

Parameter	Unit	T106C
Chord (C)	[mm]	198.0
Axial chord (C_{ax})	[mm]	170.0
Pitch (s)	[mm]	189.6
Span (h)	[mm]	375.0
Suction surface length (S_0)	[mm]	264.7
Pressure surface length	[mm]	230.0
Inlet flow angle (α_1)	[°]	32.7
Exit flow angle (α_2)	[°]	-60.4
Zweifel coefficient (Z_w)	[-]	1.30
Diffusion factor (D_V)	[-]	0.42
Diffusion rate (D_R)	[-]	0.75
Bar Diameter (ϕ)	[mm]	70.0
Bar Pitch (S_{bar})	[mm]	189.6
Axial Distance (d)	[mm]	70.0
Reduced Frequency (f_r)	[-]	0.57

FIGURE 1. Computational Domain and Boundary Conditions

multi-block in-house solver. It solves the 3D compressible Navier–Stokes equations in generalized curvilinear coordinates (Vadlamani et al. [23]). The computational setup is in line with the experimental work of Himmel [12]. The cascade specifications for the T106C configuration are provided in Table 1. Figure 1 illustrates the computational domain and the boundary conditions applied. Riemann inflow, a non-reflective boundary condition is prescribed at the inlet, while a convective outflow boundary condition is specified at the exit. No-slip boundary condition is imposed on the blade surface, and the upstream bar is

translated in the pitchwise direction with velocity U_{bar} (negative y-direction). Periodic boundary conditions are enforced in both the pitchwise and spanwise directions. Furthermore, riblets are incorporated along the suction side of the turbine blade to investigate their influence on the boundary-layer dynamics and overall aerodynamic performance. The spanwise extent of the domain is 15% C_{ax} , which is sufficient to capture the evolution of the dominant instability modes [24, 25].

All length scales are non-dimensionalized with the axial chord, C_{ax} . The Reynolds number Re_C is defined based on the true chord, C , and the isentropic exit velocity V_{2is} , given by

$$Re = \frac{\rho V_{2is} C}{\mu} \quad (1)$$

is 0.9×10^5 , and the corresponding $Re_{C_{ax}}$ is 0.77×10^5 .

FIGURE 2. Riblet geometry used in the present study: (a) suction surface of the blade for smooth and riblet configurations, (b) cross-section of scalloped riblet, (c) side view showing the ramp joining smooth and ribbed surface, and (d) inset showing the placement of riblets on the T106C blade.

TABLE 2. Summary of various configurations studied

Description	Abbreviation
Baseline configuration without wakes	BL
Baseline configuration with wakes ($f_r = 0.57$)	BLW
BLW with post-reattachment riblets	PoReRib
BLW with peak-suction riblets	PeSuRib

FIGURE 3. Cross-sectional view of the computational mesh for the smooth and ribbed blade surfaces.

Table 2 summarizes the configurations investigated in this study. This comprises a baseline configuration without wakes (BL) and with wakes (BLW). Two additional configurations are considered: one in which the riblets are placed downstream of the reattachment (PoReRib) and the other in which the riblets are placed from the location of peak suction (PeSuRib). Figure 2 (a) compares smooth, PoReRib and PeSuRib configurations. Scallop-shaped riblets are used in the current study (see Figure 2 (b)), which have been shown to be more effective than saw-tooth riblets [22]. Figure 2 (c) provides a side view, showing recessed riblets on the blade surface to avoid additional losses that typically occur for the protruded riblets [26]. To minimize any additional losses generated due to abrupt surface transition, a gradual ramp is employed to facilitate a smooth transition from the blade surface to the ribbed surface. Figure 2 (d) provides a magnified view of the riblets, highlighting their placement on the blade surface.

Figure 3 shows the meshing on the smooth and ribbed-blade surfaces. A curvilinear body-fitted mesh is used to resolve the recessed riblets. Each riblet is resolved using 32 points in the span to accurately capture the flow field within the grooves. The spacing and height of the riblets in the viscous units are indicated by $s^+ = su_\tau/\nu$ and $h^+ = hu_\tau/\nu$, respectively. Ananth et al. [21] explored several riblet configurations with varying h^+ and s^+ and reported that $h^+ \approx 22$, $s^+ \approx 17$ are optimal to reduce skin friction drag. Their study further demonstrates that taller riblets increase pressure losses, while shorter ones are ineffective in lifting near-wall vortices to provide a significant drag reduction. Taking into account the trade-off between drag reduction and additional pressure losses, the spacing and height of the riblet in the present study are set to $s^+ \approx 17$ and $h^+ \approx 10$ for both the PoReRib and PeSuRib configurations.

We employ an overset grid strategy [27] to resolve the blade. Additionally, a sliding interface is used to convect the wakes shed from the upstream bars onto the T106C blade. The overset grid reduces the overall mesh count and avoids complex meshing challenges when using a structured finite-difference solver. The sliding interface enables communication between stationary and

TABLE 3. Grid details for different configurations

Grid	Block (nbl)	Grid Size (NI × NJ × NK)
Grid A	1	465 × 300 × 64
	2	465 × 201 × 64
Total points: 14,909,760		
Grid B	1	465 × 300 × 64
	2	737 × 301 × 64
Total points: 23,119,168		
Grid C	1	127 × 300 × 576
	2	101 × 101 × 576
	3	424 × 300 × 576
	4	465 × 201 × 576
Total points: 154,895,616		

moving blocks, which is key to performing moving-body simulations. Table 3 provides the details of the various grid configurations. Grids A and B consist of two blocks each, used for simulations of flow past the T106C blade in the absence of wakes. Figure 4 (a) shows this 2-block setup: a background H-mesh (Block-1) discretized using $465 \times 300 \times 65$ points and an overlapping O-mesh (Block-2) around the T106C blade consisting of $465 \times 201 \times 65$ points. The H-grid is stretched at the outlet to minimize reflections. The O-mesh is orthogonal to the wall with a first-cell height of 10^{-4} ($y^+ \approx 0.5$). The overset grid methodology implemented in COMPSQUARE identifies the non-physical, discretization and interpolation points on the overlapping grids. A fourth-order Lagrange interpolation is established in the overlapping regions [27] to enable communication between blocks. Compared to the two-block setup, the wake-resolving simulations employ additional H-mesh and O-mesh around the cylinder. A sliding interface with a 4-point overlap is implemented to simulate moving bars. A 4-point overlap is established across the sliding interface between the background blocks (Blocks 1 and 3) to ensure accurate convection of the wakes shed by the bar. For all simulations with riblets, Grid-C (comprising nearly 155 million grid points) is used. The number of points in the span is increased from 64 to 576 to accurately resolve the flow over the riblets, with each riblet resolved using 32 points.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Validation of the numerical framework

Figure 5 (a) compares the distribution of the pressure coefficient on the blade with the experimental measurements of Himmel [12] at Re_C 0.9×10^5 and 1.2×10^5 . Sensitivity to

FIGURE 4. Numerical setup for (a) BL and (b) BLW configurations.

FIGURE 5. Pressure coefficient distribution over the suction surface of the smooth T106C blade for Grid A and Grid B at $Re = 0.9 \times 10^5$ and 1.2×10^5 . Experimental measurements from Himmel [12] are overlaid for comparison. The negative streamwise velocity region is shown in the inset, highlighting the extent of the separation.

grid resolution is also demonstrated for both Reynolds numbers. At $Re_C = 0.9 \times 10^5$, the results on both grids A and B match well with the experimental data. For a higher Reynolds number, $Re_C = 1.2 \times 10^5$, the results are more accurate on Grid B and align closely with the experimental data. Grid A underes-

FIGURE 6. Pressure coefficient distribution plotted over 16 phases within a single wake passing, compared against the time-averaged solution.

FIGURE 7. Time-averaged boundary layer profiles at nine stations along the suction surface ($S/S_0 = 0.1$ to 0.9) for the BL and BLW configurations

timates suction side separation, resulting in a smaller plateau in the C_p distribution and faster pressure recovery. The inset contours highlight the extent of the separation bubble using contours of negative u -velocity. As expected, the size of the separation bubble decreases with increasing Reynolds number. Although simulations were performed at two Reynolds numbers, subsequent simulations with wakes and riblets are carried out for $Re_C = 0.9 \times 10^5$. Hence, Grid A is used for the BLW and Grid C (with refined spanwise resolution to capture riblets) is used for the PoReRib and PeSuRib cases.

FIGURE 8. Skin-friction velocity u_τ distribution along the blade surface for the BL testcase.

3.2 Effect of wakes on unsteady loading and skin-friction

In Himmel's experiments [12], moving bars are used to study the wake-induced transition on a T106C cascade. In line with the experiments, the velocity of the cylinder bar in current simulations is set to $U_{bar} \approx 0.546$, resulting in a reduced frequency of $f_r = U_{bar}C/s_{bar}V_{2is} = 0.57$. Figure 6 compares the pressure loading on the suction surface at 16 different phases. The corresponding time-averaged profile, obtained over five wake passing (≈ 10 flow-through times where 1 through flow is C_{ax}/V_{2is}). As the wake (also referred to as 'negative jets' in the literature) convects across the separation bubble, the blade loading varies with phase due to local acceleration and deceleration induced by the wake. When the wake impinges on the suction side separation bubble, it intensifies Kelvin-Helmholtz (KH) instability in the separated shear layer, leading to stronger roll-ups. These energetic KH vortices convect downstream across the bubble and cause large unsteady pressure fluctuations on the blade surface.

To analyze the development of the boundary layer, Fig. 7 shows the streamwise velocity profiles ($u_{tangential}/U_{edge}$) at different stations along the suction surface, ranging from $0.1 \leq S/S_0 \leq 0.9$. As expected, an early transition from laminar to turbulence is evident in the BLW testcase, resulting in a thinner boundary layer and a reduced extent of the separation bubble (as highlighted by the shaded region within the range $0.6 \leq S/S_0 \leq 0.8$). At $S/S_0 = 0.9$, the flow is already turbulent in the BLW case, while the BL case still shows signs of the separation bubble.

FIGURE 9. a) Pressure coefficient distribution along the T106C blade surface for BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib cases. Enlarged view shown for b) PoReRib c) PeSuRib configurations.

3.3 Impact of wake-induced transition and ribbed-surface on T106C

In this section, we examine the efficacy of riblets as a passive flow control strategy to minimise losses on the T106C blade. Although wake interactions suppress the separation bubble and promote an early transition, they also increase the turbulent wetted area and the associated viscous losses. To mitigate these losses, as illustrated in Figure 2, riblets are introduced to reduce skin-friction drag by modifying the near-wall surface. As mentioned in section 2, two configurations are considered: one in which the riblets are placed downstream of the reattachment (PoReRib) and the other in which the riblets start from the peak suction location (PeSuRib). The flow for both these configurations (PoReRib and PeSuRib) is also averaged for around five wake-passing cycles. Riblet spacing is estimated using the relation $s^+ = su_\tau/\nu$, where u_τ is the friction velocity obtained from the BL test case. As shown in Fig. 8, the BL case yielded $u_\tau \approx 0.027$ in the turbulent regime. Based on this value, around 18 riblets could be accommodated within the span of $\approx 0.15C_{ax}$.

Figure 9 (a) shows the pressure coefficient on the blade surface for four test cases: BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib. As discussed earlier, the separation bubble is significantly reduced in the BLW case compared to that in the BL case. For the ribbed blades, local spikes in the pressure coefficient are observable, which can be correlated to the locations at which the flow con-

FIGURE 10. Vorticity magnitude contours for the four configurations: BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib.

ducts from a smooth to a ribbed surface. As shown in the enlarged view of C_p in Fig. 9 (b,c), these spikes are minimal when the riblets are placed after reattachment (PoReRib), while the spikes are more pronounced for the PeSuRib configuration. In fact, the flow in the PeSuRib case undergoes an early transition over the riblets, thereby suppressing the separation bubble.

Figure 10 shows the vorticity magnitude contours that indicate the effect of riblets on the blade suction surface. It is evident that the wakes, or ‘negative jets’, help to reduce the size of the laminar separation bubble. Nevertheless, when riblets are introduced, the vorticity magnitude downstream of $S/S_0 \approx 0.8$ drops significantly near the wall. To examine this in detail, five equidistant slices are extracted along the streamwise direction ($0.5 < S/S_0 < 0.9$), as shown in Fig. 11. using contours of time-averaged vorticity. In the BLW configuration, the flow remains laminar up to $S/S_0 = 0.5$. The shear layer separates at $S/S_0 = 0.6$. It destabilizes downstream and triggers the transition to turbulence. The flow reattaches around $S/S_0 \sim 0.8$, resulting in a larger ω_{mag} near the wall. For the PoReRib case, high vorticity is confined to the riblet tips, reducing the overall turbulent wetted area. Furthermore, the PeSuRib surface undergoes an early transition. Turbulence develops as early as $S/S_0 = 0.7$, with the vortices adhering primarily to the riblet tips, while the valleys remain relatively undisturbed. At $S/S_0 = 0.9$, the same pattern as that of PoReRib persists, with a high vorticity confined to the riblet tips and minimal activity within the valleys. These observations indicate that the vortices are effectively displaced

FIGURE 11. Streamwise evolution of flow transition shown at five z -planes located between $S/S_0 = 0.5$ and $S/S_0 = 0.9$ for BLW, PoReRib and PeSuRib configurations.

over the riblet tips thereby reducing the turbulence wetted area.

Figure 12 depicts the space-time evolution of the skin-friction coefficient (C_f) on the blade suction surface for the three configurations (BLW, PoReRib and PeSuRib) for five wake-passing cycles. Regions of negative C_f correspond to flow separation over the suction surface. It is evident that flow reattachment is promoted during wake passing. In between the wake-passings, a prolonged separation is evident for all the cases. A reduction in C_f for the PoReRib configuration is observable between $0.8 < S/S_0 < 1$ compared to the BLW case. However, for the PeSuRib case, the extent of separation is relatively smaller and a region of enhanced C_f is evident between $(0.6 < S/S_0 < 0.8)$ due to the early transition over riblets. Figure 13 compares the streamwise variation of time-averaged skin-friction coefficient from the suction surface for different test cases. As expected, all the cases with wakes show a substantial reduction in the separation bubble relative to the baseline (BL) case. Both PoReRib and PeSuRib exhibit spikes in C_f at the location of the initiation of the ribs. For PeSuRib, the laminar separation bubble shifts upstream, promoting an earlier transition. Between

$S/S_0 = 0.85 - 0.95$, note that the C_f for the PoReRib case is much lower than the BLW case. This indicates an encouraging reduction in viscous losses in the post-reattachment region with riblets.

Figure 14 (a) compares the time and span-averaged contours of the turbulent kinetic energy (k) for all test cases. The pre-transitional fluctuations in the separated shear layer are minimal in the BL case because of the lack of any free-stream turbulence. For all other cases, the pre-transitional fluctuations are prominent due to the wake-induced Klebanoff modes that accelerate transition when interacting with the KH modes. Hence, the BL case exhibits the steepest growth of k as the transition is governed predominantly by the KH instability, while the PeSuRib configuration exhibits the lowest slope where the multi-mode transition is triggered under the combined influence of Klebanoff and KH modes. No significant TKE generation occurs at the riblet onset for either of the riblet cases. This becomes more clear in Fig. 14 (b), which compares the streamwise evolution of the maximum turbulent kinetic energy (k_{max}). In particular, the peak k_{max} is significantly lower and is shifted upstream for the PeSuRib case.

FIGURE 12. Time evolution of the skin-friction coefficient (C_f) over the blade suction surface for the three configurations (BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib).

FIGURE 13. Coefficient of friction (C_f) distribution along the T106C blade suction surface for BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib configurations.

The PoReRib case shows a marginal deviation from the BLW in the turbulent regime, although the trends remain similar across different test cases.

3.4 Profile Loss Estimation

Denton [28] expressed the overall profile loss, ζ_{loss} , as follows:

FIGURE 14. a) Turbulent Kinetic Energy contours for the four configurations: BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib. Marker shows the onset of riblets b) Maximum turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) along the suction surface.

$$\zeta_{loss} = \left[\frac{C_{pb}t}{s \cos \alpha_2} + \frac{2(\theta_{SS} + \theta_{PS})}{s \cos \alpha_2} + \left(\frac{\delta_{SS}^* + \delta_{PS}^* + t}{s \cos \alpha_2} \right)^2 \right] \frac{P_{01} - P_{TE}}{P_{01} - P_{mix}} \quad (2)$$

The terms in the RHS of the equation 2 represent the profile loss due to (i) the base pressure $Loss_{BP}$ at the trailing edge, (ii) the momentum thickness $Loss_{\theta}$, and (iii) the displacement thickness $Loss_{\delta^*}$ from the suction and pressure sides. The last term outside the parentheses is the scaling factor. In equation 2, t is the trailing-edge thickness, α_2 is the outlet flow angle, θ and δ^* are

TABLE 4. Loss decomposition on the T106C blade for four configurations: BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib.

Config	$Loss_{BP}$	BP (%)	$Loss_{\theta}$	θ (%)	$Loss_{\delta^*}$	δ^* (%)	τ_{loss}	Δ Loss vs BL (%)	Δ Loss vs BLW (%)
BL	-0.0026	-7.43	0.033	96.18	0.0039	11.26	0.034	0.00	13.33
BLW	-0.0022	-7.30	0.028	95.58	0.0035	11.71	0.030	-14.10	0.00
PoReRib	-0.0019	-5.87	0.031	92.55	0.0044	13.32	0.033	-4.63	10.00
PeSuRib	-0.0018	-4.72	0.035	90.96	0.0054	13.79	0.039	12.34	30.00

FIGURE 15. Displacement thickness and momentum thickness distributions along the suction surface of the blade for the four configurations (BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib).

the momentum and displacement thicknesses on the suction (SS) and pressure (PS) surfaces close to the trailing edge, respectively, and C_{pb} is the base pressure coefficient. P_{01} is measured $0.2C_{ax}$ upstream of the T106C leading edge, P_{mix} is the mixed-out averaged value measured $0.3C_{ax}$ downstream of the trailing edge, and P_{TE} is measured at the trailing edge. Details of the Loss calculations are provided in [12].

Figure 15 shows the streamwise variation of displacement and momentum thicknesses over the suction surface of the T106C blade. A distinct increase in δ^* is observed at the riblet onset location, highlighting an increase in $Loss_{\delta^*}$. In contrast, the momentum thickness θ exhibits a marginal increase, indicating that the loss contribution due to θ is minimal due to the placement of the riblet.

Table 4 summarizes the decomposition of profile loss into base pressure, $Loss_{\theta}$, and $Loss_{\delta^*}$. Figure 16 highlights two distinct trends in loss decomposition. Introducing wakes (BLW)

reduces both $Loss_{\theta}$ and $Loss_{\delta^*}$, resulting in a 14.10% drop in total loss relative to the BL case. This case is found to be superior to the riblet cases: PoReRib and PeSuRib. For the PoReRib case, the total loss decreased by 4.63% relative to the BL case. In contrast, the total loss for the PeSuRib case increased by 12.34% due to early transition which increased both the δ^* and the θ related losses. Figure 17 shows that the contribution due to suction surface boundary layer $Loss_{\theta_{SS}}$ is dominant, accounting for 82.8–85% in all cases. The pressure side loss $Loss_{\theta}$ is consistently small (2.0–6.7%). For the BLW case, $Loss_{\delta^*}$ increased marginally to 10.9% compared to the BL case (10.5%). However, for the configurations with riblets a significant increase was observed ($\geq 12.6\%$). $Loss_{\delta^*}$ was the largest for the PeSuRib case (13.2%) indicating a sharp increase in δ^* . When compared to the BLW case, the overall losses for the PoReRib and PeSuRib cases approximately increased by 10% and 30%, respectively. These results demonstrate that the effectiveness of riblets in controlling viscous losses is critically dependent on their placement and interaction with the transitional boundary layer affected by upstream wakes. Although both the PoReRib and PeSuRib cases show a reduction in local skin friction (C_f), the overall profile loss remains slightly higher than the BLW case. This behaviour may be attributed to the fact that while the riblets effectively lift near-wall vortices and reduce local turbulent shear, the surface transition from smooth to rough surface might still play a major role. To address these issues, future work will look at the effects of employing riblets with optimal ramp design and height. So far we have not observed any significant benefit of riblets in a time-averaged sense. Consequently, further analysis is performed on individual phases within the wake-passing cycle to identify phases where the riblets could be beneficial.

3.5 Phase-averaged exit loss characteristics

This section examines the influence of wake position on the skin-friction distribution for smooth and ribbed-blade configurations, along with the associated total pressure loss at the exit plane. A total of sixteen snapshots were recorded within each wake-passing cycle, and phase-averaged results for five such wake-passing cycles were obtained. Figure 18 shows the vorticity magnitude contours for phases 4, 8, 12, and 16, illustrating the wake position relative to the blade surface. The spanwise

FIGURE 16. Loss analysis for the four configurations (BL, BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib).

FIGURE 17. Loss Breakdown within the boundary layer.

and phase-averaged skin-friction (C_f) distribution shows negative values for phase 4, indicating that the incoming wake has not yet interacted with the separation bubble (although the bubble size over the riblets in the case PeSuRib is very small). The corresponding stagnation pressure contours at the exit plane exhibit

a qualitatively similar behavior. The loss coefficient at the exit (located $0.3C_{ax}$ downstream of the trailing edge) ζ_{exit} , is evaluated as follows:

$$\zeta_{exit} = \frac{P_{01} - P_{0,mix}}{P_{01} - P_{mix}}. \quad (3)$$

where $P_{0,mix}$ refers to the stagnation pressure values at the exit plane.

Figure 18 shows the pitchwise distribution of ζ_{exit} . Comparison of phase- and span-averaged loss profiles from three and five wake-passing profiles demonstrates that the results are statistically converged. It is evident that the PeSuRib configuration consistently exhibits higher losses across all phases compared to the BLW and PoReRib cases. In contrast, PoReRib yields losses comparable to those of the BLW configuration, across most of the phases except at phase 8. Note that ζ_{exit} exhibits a delayed response to wake-blade interactions and therefore wake-induced losses can be directly correlated with the skin-friction behaviour in the previous phase. At phase 8, the wake interacts with the separation bubble and promotes attached flow for all cases, as evident in the C_f distribution (highlighted as ROI-A). Its effect manifests itself as a reduction in the total pressure loss

FIGURE 18. Phase-averaged flow comparison over five wake-passing cycles for three different configurations (BLW, PoReRib, and PeSuRib). Stagnation pressure contours are extracted from a location $0.3C_{ax}$ downstream of the trailing edge. ROI denotes region of interest.

in the exit plane (as is evident from the contours P_0) in phase 12 (highlighted as ROI-B), indicating a reduction in loss for the PoReRib configuration. At phase 12, the wake shown in phase 8 has passed over the separation bubble, while a new incoming wake approaches the leading edge. The corresponding C_f distribution at phase 12 reveals that the separation bubble attempts to re-establish itself and grows in size following the wake passing over the blade. The associated exit-plane loss profiles at phase 16 indicate that once the wake has passed over the separation bubble, all configurations, smooth and ribbed, exhibit similar loss levels. The skin-friction distribution of phase 16 indicates that the separation bubble re-establishes itself. Consequently, the exit-plane losses associated with phase 4 indicate higher losses for the PeSuRib configuration, consistent with the observations of the time-averaged statistics (see Figure 16).

The performance improvement associated with PoReRib was observed during phase 8, where the wake–boundary layer interaction effectively suppressed the separation bubble and the boundary layer remained laminar and attached over a longer extent of the blade. Analysis of the space-time contours of the skin friction coefficient (C_f) in Figure 12 indicates that for the reduced frequency under consideration ($f_r = 0.57$), the separation region persists over an extended portion of the wake cycle, while the duration of the wake-induced attached flow remains relatively short. An increase in the reduced frequency, or operation under elevated free-stream turbulence (FST) levels, is ex-

pected to amplify the wake-induced reattachment mechanism, thereby enhancing the performance of the PoReRib configuration. In contrast, the PeSuRib case continues to exhibit higher total losses, suggesting that its performance sensitivity requires further investigation through optimisation of the ramp function and riblet height parameters.

4 Summary and conclusion

A series of implicit large-eddy simulations (ILES) were carried out to investigate the individual and combined effects of wakes and riblets on boundary layer transition over a T106C cascade. Overset mesh and sliding interface techniques were implemented in the in-house solver, and the computational framework was validated against the experimental measurements of Himmel [12]. Four test cases were studied at $Re_C = 0.9 \times 10^5$. These include the baseline without wakes (BL), the baseline with wakes at a reduced frequency of $f_r = 0.57$ (BLW), and the two riblet-modified cases with wakes: one in which the riblets, of sizes $s^+ \approx 17$ and $h^+ \approx 10$, are placed downstream of reattachment (PoReRib) and the other in which the riblets start from peak suction location (PeSuRib).

A comparison between BL and BLW revealed that wakes reduced the size of the laminar separation bubble (LSB), resulting in a decrease in C_f post reattachment. Both riblet configurations effectively lifted near-wall vortices, restricted their penetration into the valleys, thereby reducing the turbulent wetted

area specifically in the post-transition regime. For the PeSuRib case, the transition shifted significantly upstream increasing the turbulent wetted area. As expected, the total profile loss for the BL case is higher by 13.3% relative to the BLW case. However, despite the reduction in skin friction, the profile loss analysis depicted contrasting trends. For the PoReRib and PeSuRib cases, the losses increased by 10.00% and 30% compared to the BLW case. Despite a reduction in C_f , these counterintuitive trends in losses occurred due to the early transition in the PeSuRib case. Denton’s profile loss decomposition further showed that the riblets examined in the current study, while effective in reducing turbulent wetted area, increased the displacement and momentum thickness contributions to the overall loss.

While the time-averaged statistics suggest increased overall losses, the phase-averaged analysis reveals the benefit of riblets during certain phases of wake passing. The PoReRib configuration exhibited a localised benefit during the phase in which the wake interaction effectively suppressed the separation bubble. This behavior suggests that as the reduced frequency of wakes or FST levels increases, the PoReRib case will likely mitigate losses over an extended period, resulting in enhanced performance. However, the PeSuRib case remained more loss generating, indicating the need for further refinement in riblet height and ramp function. Unlike the $h^+ = 10$ riblet configuration examined in the current study, future studies will focus on incorporating optimal dimensions as reported in the studies of Ananth et al. [21]. Furthermore, modifying the linear ramp to a cosine function ramp can possibly reduce the boundary layer losses.

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